

Exploring the Drip Point in Neutron Stars via a Modified Semi-Empirical Mass Formula

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The realistic case of nuclei, rather than free protons, capturing the electrons is investigated by extrapolating the semi-empirical mass formula of nuclei to the case of neutron-rich nuclei. Beyond a critical density new neutrons produced by capture can not form bound states with the nuclei and drip out. The neutron drip transition is crucial for determining the crustal composition and have been investigated by using several approaches in the literature. These approaches confirm that the transition is highly sensitive to the semi-empirical mass formula which determines the binding energy of the nuclei. To determine the crustal composition a modified version of the semi-empirical mass formula, obtained by a genetic algorithm rather than a Bayesian neural network or any other method, is employed. This version of the mass formula involves a modification of the liquid drop model by considering an asymmetry and deformation of the nucleons at the limit of stability and adds extra terms to the surface energy. The narrowing of the valley of stability, revealing a shift in the neutron drip line to lower mass numbers and an increase in neutron drip density, is investigated. Recent results in the context of displacive ferroelectric materials such as BaTiO₃ are discussed for the possible compositions of the neutron star crusts.

I. INTRODUCTION

In compact objects both quantum mechanics and the nuclear physics play crucial roles in determining the state of matter with contributions from all known fundamental forces (gravitation, electromagnetism, weak and strong interactions). The density of matter at the core of neutron stars exceeds 10^{15} g cm⁻³. There are currently no terrestrial experiments which can produce matter at such densities.

The crustal composition of neutron stars control the thermal and electric transport properties of matter in the crust as well as the dynamics of superfluid neutron vortices which are relevant to the observed thermal and rotational evolution of neutron stars. The onset of neutron drip in dense matter is therefore of utmost importance for modeling these observed phenomena. This transition is generally found to occur at the density $\rho_{\text{drip}} \simeq 4.3 \times 10^{11}$ g cm⁻³ as discussed in [1].

II. HARRISON-WHEELER EQUATION OF STATE

At densities near the neutron drip point $\sim 3-4 \times 10^{11}$ g cm⁻³, relativistic electrons, nuclei and neutrons coexist together to determine the state of lowest energy. When the density exceeds this point more pressure is caused by free neutrons than by electrons. Thus, the total energy density can be written as

$$\epsilon = \underbrace{n_N M(A, Z)c^2}_{\text{nuclei}} + \underbrace{\epsilon_e^*(n_e)}_{\text{electrons}} + \underbrace{\epsilon_n(n_n)}_{\text{neutrons}} \quad (1)$$

where n_N is the number density of nuclei and $M(A, Z)$ is the mass of a nucleus (A, Z) which will be investigated in detail in the later section. Since $M(A, Z)$ includes electron rest mass, ϵ_e^* denotes the energy density of electrons with the subtraction of their rest mass $n_e m_e c^2$ [2].

$$\epsilon_e^* = \epsilon_e(n_e) - n_e m_e c^2. \quad (2)$$

Useful relations for baryon number density n_b and the fractions are given by

$$n_b = n_N A + n_n, \quad n_N = \frac{n_e}{Z} \quad (3)$$

$$Y_n = 1 - AY_N, \quad Y_N = \frac{Y_e}{Z} \quad (4)$$

where n_n is the number density of free neutrons and Y_n is the fraction of the free neutrons. The electron density per proton gives the number density of nuclei n_N .

The Harrison-Wheeler equation of state is composed of 3 set of equations

$$\epsilon = \frac{n_b(1 - Y_n)}{A} M(A, Z)c^2 + \epsilon_e^*(n_e) + \epsilon_n(n_n), \quad (5)$$

$$P = P_e + P_n, \quad (6)$$

$$n = \frac{A}{Z} n_e + n_n. \quad (7)$$

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A. Neutron drip

We have stated that the point where the free neutrons appear plays an important role on the compositions of the boundary between the outer and inner crusts. We begin with writing the total energy density

$$\epsilon = \frac{n(1 - Y_n)}{A} M(A, Z) c^2 + \epsilon_e^*(n_e) + \epsilon_n(n_n) + \epsilon_L. \quad (8)$$

When the fraction of neutrons Y_n reach its maximum, the transition occurs. Following relations are needed to proceed

$$\frac{\partial \epsilon_e^*}{\partial n_e} = \frac{\epsilon_e^* + P}{n_e}, \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{\partial \epsilon_n}{\partial n_n} = E_{F,n}. \quad (10)$$

Neglecting the lattice energy and considering A and Z as continuous variables Harrison and Wheeler have found that the neutron drip occurs when the following relations are satisfied [2]

$$\frac{\partial M(A, Z)}{\partial A} c^2 = E_{F,n}, \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{\partial M(A, Z)}{\partial A} = m_n, \quad p_{F,n} \rightarrow 0. \quad (12)$$

B. Modified mass formula

The effect of the total mass of the nucleus $M(A, Z)$ to the Gibbs free energy can be seen implicitly from the previous calculations. So the determination of the mass of

$$E_b = a_v A - a_s A^{2/3} - a_c (Z^2 - Z) A^{-1/3} - a_a (A - 2Z)^2 A^{-1} + a_p A^{-1/2} \quad (15)$$

where the pairing term takes the value $\pm a_p$ depending on the even or odd number of nucleons.

C. Correction due to the deformation

Even if the most common perception of a neutron star is that of a uniform assembly of neutrons exist at high densities, nuclei at the limit of stability have a crucial

$$E_b^* = a_v A - a_s A^{2/3} - a_c \frac{(Z^2 - Z)}{(1 + \Delta)} A^{-1/3} - \frac{\alpha}{1 + \frac{\alpha}{\beta} A^{-1/3}} (A - 2Z)^2 A^{-1} \pm a_p A^{-1/2} \quad (16)$$

where the corrections α is the volume symmetry and β

the nucleus gives a better idea about the crustal composition of a compact star and the neutron drip transitions. The semi-empirical mass formula was originally proposed by Gamow and later improved by Weizsäcker, Bethe and Bacher [3]. Considering the nuclei as an *incompressible spherical liquid drops* of uniform density the liquid drop model (LDM) was also constructed as a simple nuclear model that can predict the binding energy of many nuclei and explains many nuclear and astrophysical phenomena. The LDM is improved by the addition of the empirical terms and led to the semi-empirical mass formula which can be written as

$$M(A, Z) = m_n(A - Z) + m_H Z - \frac{E_b}{c^2} \quad (13)$$

where E_b is the binding energy and composed of empirical parameters that represent volume, surface, Coulomb, asymmetry, and pairing contributions. Predictions can be improved by selecting a better combination of these coefficients with reliable algorithms. The effects of these mass models on crustal compositions are recently investigated with the methods such as Bayesian Neural Network method (BNN) [4], Duflou-Zuker (DZ) [5] and other formalisms with trace formulas [6]. Authors [7] employed the genetic algorithm (GA) to determine the binding energies. GA is a stochastic method inspired by the theory of evolution (see [8] for an introduction to the method). In this work, we use the SEMF obtained by [9] to determine the crustal composition. Standard form of the binding energy can be written as

$$E_b = E_v - E_s - E_c - E_a - E_p. \quad (14)$$

If we write each term explicitly, we get

nucleon asymmetry and it is deformed. For nuclei that contain excess of neutrons over protons the radius of the neutron distribution is larger than that of the proton distribution. The half-density radii for neutrons R_n and protons R_p for asymmetrical nuclei invalidates the surface tension term $-a_s A^{2/3}$. Thus, an additional correction is included in the SEMF to account for these different nuclear surfaces [9]. Binding energy with the correction coefficients is given

is the surface symmetry parameters. For symmetrical

nuclei $\beta \rightarrow \infty$, $\Delta = 0$ and $\alpha = a_a$. This is the direct result of the GA eliminating the asymmetry skin. The term Δ includes Coulomb corrections due to the proton radii change. Table I contains the coefficients obtained from the GA.

TABLE I. LDM coefficients obtained from the GA for standard and the modified SEMF [7].

[MeV]	a_v	a_s	a_c	a_a	α	β	a_p
St.form	15.19	16.51	0.675	20.72	-	-	12.53
$\Delta = 0$	15.23	16.75	0.668	-	24.97	30.99	11.10

Now, inserting the binding energy given in Equation 16 to Equation 13 the effect of the modified SEMF to the neutron drip transition in neutron stars can be investigated using the corresponding coefficients given in Table I. We define parameters as

$$\begin{aligned} \xi &= 15.19 - 11.1A^{-1/3} + 0.223(Z^2 - Z)A^{-4/3}, \\ \phi &= -\frac{(A - 2Z)^2 \alpha \left(\frac{2\alpha}{A^{1/3}\beta} + 3 \right)}{3 \left(A + \frac{A^{2/3}\alpha}{\beta} \right)^2}, \\ \gamma &= \frac{2(A - 2Z)\alpha}{A + \frac{A^{2/3}\alpha}{\beta}} + \frac{1}{2}A^{-3/2}a_p. \end{aligned}$$

So, the following relation gives the drip point element according to the Equation 12

$$\{\xi - \phi + \gamma\}_{A_{drip}, Z_{drip}} = 0. \quad (17)$$

Binding energies corresponding to the standard and the modified versions of SEMF are calculated using the relations given in Equation 15 and Equation 16. The valley of stability diagram representing the binding energy per nucleon is given in Figure 1 for both E_b and E_b^* .

III. CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSIONS

Modified SEMF results

In § II B, we applied a modified version of SEMF to the equation of state of neutron stars for the determination of the possible crustal compositions. The mass model we have applied was only sensitive in the $20 \lesssim Z \lesssim 60$ range. Whereas the composition of the outer layers of the crust is not sensitive to SEMF, the EOS becomes highly mass sensitive at the inner crust. The modified SEMF, which incorporates an asymmetry term optimized via a genetic algorithm, shifts and narrows the valley of stability. If the neutron drip line moves to lower neutron numbers, the most likely reason is an increase in the asymmetry energy penalty, since that term directly affects neutron-rich nuclei. As a result, binding energy per nucleon decreases faster as neutron number increases. The modified SEMF model predicts less stability for extremely neutron-rich nuclei, meaning they reach the drip line sooner than expected. Deformation of a nuclei is still an unsolved issue of nuclear physics. How the neutrons and protons distributed in the deformation process is still unknown. Most of the modified version of the mass formula do include the deformation but do not, in general, include the fact that this deformation can be asymmetric. Typical SEMF modifications to the volume or surface terms would shift the entire binding energy curve, but not necessarily impact neutron-rich nuclei in this specific way. The Coulomb term mainly affects proton-heavy nuclei, and the pairing term introduces fine corrections rather than a large-scale shift. Our results indicate that the deforming nuclei might not be in perfect peanut shape. The elements found for the transitions, form the key components of iron-based superconductors such as alkali metal iron selenides ($A\text{Fe}_x\text{-Se}_2$) [10]. Recent results in the context of ferroelectric materials such as BaTiO_3 [11] [12] also showed that there might be structural deformations from the undistorted cubic structure under high pressures.

FIG. 1. Binding energy per nucleon for the standard, E_b , and the modified binding energies E_b^* .

Slightly higher drip density could indicate that the nuclei near the drip line are more densely packed. This means that while nuclei reach the drip line faster, there is a greater population of unstable nuclei closer to the boundary, contributing to the higher drip density. These results are indicating that the equilibrium structure might be similar to that in displacive ferroelectric materials [13]. The shift in the neutron drip line alters the composition of neutron star crusts, leading to different nuclear reactions and thermal properties, which impact cooling rates and magnetic field evolution. As we have mentioned, if barium titanate were a possible neutron star crust composition, its high dielectric constant could influence the star's electric and magnetic field dynamics, potentially affecting magnetar activity. Additionally, its presence might alter thermal conductivity and shear modulus, impacting glitches and gravitational wave emissions. More importantly, its piezoelectric properties could play a role in how stress accumulates and releases, possibly affecting the frequency and intensity of glitches. These findings highlight the role of SEMF in identifying stability trends and possible nuclear boundary transitions, which impacts both theoretical nuclear physics and astrophysical models.

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AVAILABILITY OF CODE

Our code calculates the modified semi-empirical mass formula (SEMF) for a range of isotopes with atomic numbers (Z) and mass numbers (A) from 1 to 130, generating a matrix of SEMF values. The matrix has a size of 131x131. It identifies the specific isotope with the minimal SEMF value in absolute terms, highlighting the Barium isotope ($A=106$, $Z=56$) as the one closest to zero, providing insights into the behavior of nuclear binding energy across isotopes. The code used in this research can be made available upon request.

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- [1] B. C. Coşkun, Physics of neutron star crusts (2017), unpublished thesis, Istanbul Technical University.
- [2] S. L. Shapiro and S. A. Teukolsky, *Black Holes, White Dwarfs, and Neutron Stars: the Physics of Compact Objects* (John Wiley, 1983).
- [3] K. Oyamatsu, K. Iida, and H. Koura, Neutron drip line and the equation of state of nuclear matter, *Phys. Rev. C* **82**, 027301 (2010), arXiv:1005.3183 [nucl-th].
- [4] R. Utama, J. Piekarewicz, and H. B. Prosper, Nuclear Mass Predictions for the Crustal Composition of Neutron Stars: A Bayesian Neural Network Approach, *ArXiv e-prints* (2015), arXiv:1508.06263 [nucl-th].
- [5] C. Qi, A short explanation of the Duflo-Zuker mass model, *ArXiv e-prints* (2014), arXiv:1407.8218 [nucl-th].
- [6] A. Bhagwat, Simple nuclear mass formula, *Phys. Rev. C* **90**, 064306 (2014).
- [7] C. Daley, *An improved Mass formula*, Ph.D. thesis, The University of Surrey (2004).
- [8] M. Mitchell, *An introduction to genetic algorithms*, 1996, PHI Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi (1996).
- [9] P. Danielewicz, Surface symmetry energy, *Nuclear Physics A* **727**, 233 (2003).
- [10] E. Dagotto, Colloquium: The unexpected properties of alkali metal iron selenide superconductors, *Reviews of Modern Physics* **85**, 849 (2013), arXiv:1210.6501 [cond-mat.supr-con].
- [11] G. Arlt, D. Hennings, *et al.*, Dielectric properties of fine-grained barium titanate ceramics, *Journal of applied physics* **58**, 1619 (1985).
- [12] D. Duan, X. Meng, F. Tian, C. Chen, L. Wang, Y. Ma, T. Cui, B. Liu, Z. He, and G. Zou, The crystal structure and superconducting properties of monatomic bromine, *Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter* **22**, 015702 (2010).
- [13] D. Kobyakov and C. J. Pethick, Towards a metallurgy of neutron star crusts, *Physical review letters* **112**, 112504 (2014).